

CONDUCTANCE OF SALTS IN NON-AQUEOUS SOLVENTS. PART I. CONDUCTANCE OF SALTS IN TRIETHANOLAMINE

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Conductivities of a number of electrolytes, e.g., tetraethylammonium chloride, tetraethylammonium chlorate, tetramethylammonium chloride, tetramethylammonium chlorate, tetramethylammonium perchlorate, ethylamine hydrochloride, hydrochloric acid, sulphuric acid and sodium, were determined under different experimental conditions using triethanolamine as a solvent. The equations (i) of Debye-Hückel-Onsager and (ii) of Fuoss and Kraus were tried on the experimental results. Considering the fact that the above equations are valid for strong electrolytes at large dilutions, the results which have been recorded in this part could be explained more or less satisfactorily even though the solutions studied are moderately concentrated. The variation of conductivity with increasing temperature has been found to be quite normal and the plot of $\log \kappa$ against T (temperature) passes through a maximum as in most non-aqueous solvents. Walden's rule fails completely in triethanolamine solvent. The mobility of tetraethylammonium ion in triethanolamine solvent has been calculated and found to be 0.0355.

The study of conductance in non-aqueous solutions is of importance not only for understanding the nature of these solutions but also for testing the various theories of conductance that have been developed in this field. Reference may be made to the work done by Franklin *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 27, 191; *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1888, 23, 277; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1911, 15, 675, 683; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1909, 69, 290), Hartley *et al.* (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1925, A, 109, 351; 1930, A, 126, 84; 1930, A, 127, 228; 1931, A, 132, 427; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2488, 2492; 1931, 199, 215; *Ann. Rep. Chem. Soc.*, 27, 326), Walden *et al.* (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, 114, 275, 287; 1926, 123, 429; 1931, A153, 1; 1929, A144, 262, 395; 1928, A140, 89; 1932, A 160, 337; 1930, A 147, 1) and more recently by Fuoss, Kraus and their collaborators (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 21; 1940, 62, 506, 2238) in various solvents, e. g., liquid ammonia, different alcohols, benzonitrile, sulphur dioxide, pyridine, etc. The experimental data have been used to examine critically the theories of Arrhenius (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1887, 1, 631), Debye-Hückel (*Physikal. Z.*, 1923, 24, 185, 306; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, 23, 334), Onsager (*Physikal. Z.*, 1926, 27, 368; 1927, 28, 277; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, 23, 341), and Fuoss and Kraus (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 476, 1019, 2387, 3614; 1935, 57, 1; Kraus, *Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1934, 66, 179; Fuoss, *Chem. Rev.*, 1935, 17, 27), which are based mostly on data obtained for aqueous solutions.

It has been found that in solvents other than simple alcohols, large deviations from the Debye-Hückel-Onsager's equation are common. With solvents of low dielectric constants the deviations from Onsager's equation are universal and become rapidly greater, the smaller the dielectric constant. Extremely interesting results were obtained by Kraus and Fuoss (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 21), who studied tetra-*iso*amylammonium nitrate in mixtures of dioxane and water, with dielectric constants varying from 78.6 to 2.2. Fuoss *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) have developed a theory to explain most of the experimental data in non-aqueous solvents of both high and low dielectric constants.

In the literature we do not find any data for systems where the solvent is very viscous and also where solvent molecules are large or of the same order of magnitude

as the solute molecules. Mention may be made of the studies on the conductance of some organic amine picrates and chlorides in triethyl phosphate, $(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O})_3\text{PO}_4$ [$\eta = 0.285$ poises at 40° and D (dielectric constant) = 6.92] by Elliot and Fuoss (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 294), and in monoethanolamine, $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH})\text{NH}_2$ [$\eta = 0.193$ poises and $D = 37.72$] by Brisco and Dirks (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1940, 44, 388).

It is possible that a more complete understanding of the nature of solutions can come only through experimental work extending over a variety of solvents having a wide range of viscosities and dielectric constants, and also a wide range of concentrations.

In this part data for the electrical conductivities of solutions of uni-univalent electrolytes in a very viscous solvent, triethanolamine $[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH})_3\text{N}]$, have been recorded. Triethanolamine should behave both as an alcoholic solvent as well as a strong ammoniacal base. It has an extremely high viscosity ($\eta = 8.27$ poises at 25°) and moderately high dielectric constant ($D = 29.36$ at 25°).

In the present investigation, conductivity measurements could not be made at large dilutions, due to the fact that accurate null-points could not be obtained with the Wheatstone bridge arrangement used by us.

The equations of Debye-Hückel-Onsager (i) and of Fuoss and Kraus (ii) have been tried on the experimental results. Considering the fact that (i) and (ii) are valid for strong electrolytes at large dilutions, the results which we have obtained could be explained more or less satisfactorily, even though the solutions studied are moderately concentrated and the sources of error in the measurements are numerous.

The following electrolytes have been studied: (a) tetraethylammonium chloride, (b) tetraethylammonium chlorate, (c) tetramethylammonium chloride, (d) tetramethylammonium chlorate, (e) tetramethylammonium perchlorate, (f) ethylamine hydrochloride, (g) hydrochloric acid, (h) sulphuric acid, and lastly (i) sodium.

EXPERIMENTAL

For measurement of conductivities, the Kohlrausch method was used. The bridge wire was of the drum type, 470 cm. long, of 7 ohms resistance and having an ebonite hood made by the Leeds and Northrup Co. The scale was graduated to read accurately one in 10,000. An alternating current of a standard frequency of 1000 cycles was supplied by a Leeds and Northrup microphone hammer, operated by a six volt lead accumulator battery, the frequency being controlled by a 1000 cycle tuning fork. The current had some harmonics but their effect was greatly reduced by the tunable telephone used.

Two standard decade dial resistance boxes of Leeds and Northrup, each giving 1-10,000 ohms and two standardised fixed resistances, one of 55,000 and the other of 100,000 ohms were used for known resistances in the bridge circuit, with the tuned telephone set in the detector circuit. The temperature was maintained constant within $\pm 0.05^\circ$.

The Conductivity Cell.—Being a very hygroscopic liquid and highly alkaline in nature, with a strong tendency to absorb water vapour and carbon dioxide from the atmosphere, triethanolamine must be carefully handled with

as little exposure as possible. It is very viscous and cannot be pipetted or easily transferred in any other way. The range of conductivities to be measured in the same cell was also very wide, being from 1×10^{-7} to 1×10^{-2} mhos. The electrodes should occupy therefore a very large area. The cell used was similar to the one used by Guy and Jones (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1911, 46, 131) in their investigation on glycerine. It is made of a neutral glass tube of 30 mm. diameter with a ground-glass cap, through which are passed two glass tubes (carrying the electrodes) sealed rigidly. The electrodes were made of thick platinum plates of 25 mm. diameter; two platinum leads were welded on to the plates and were fused into the glass tubes.

With unplatinised electrodes the sound minimum was not sharp enough for accurate determinations; the electrodes were therefore covered with a fine, velvety black coating of platinum, despite the fact that for alkaline solvents unplatinised electrodes are supposed to give better results.

Livingston, Morgan and Lammert (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 1692; 1924, 46, 1117) found that the method of cleansing and drying the electrodes was of very great importance, and capable of introducing errors as high as 2 to 3%.

The electrodes were first washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, then followed by washing in running water, distilled water and conductivity water. Finally they were washed with anhydrous alcohol and dried in air. Throughout the course of washing and drying and bringing the cell to the temperature of the thermostat, the electrodes were short circuited by means of a copper wire.

The Determination of the Cell Constant.—In most cases the cell constant was determined with two concentrations of KCl, 0.001*N* and 0.1*N* taking usual precautions.

Manipulation.—The cell was carefully cleansed, steamed and dried, as mentioned before. The container without the electrodes was weighed, the necessary quantity of solvent was next added and it was quickly reweighed. The ground-glass cap with the electrodes was immediately placed on, any air bubbles entrained in the liquid were removed by gently shaking and warming. The cell was then left in the thermostat for half an hour, after which the conductivity was determined.

From a weighed quantity of the electrolyte contained in a small, cleaned, steamed and dried weighing bottle, a small quantity was transferred quickly into the cell and its weight was determined by difference. The solute was dissolved by gentle shaking and warming; air bubbles were removed as before and the cell was left in the thermostat for half an hour and the conductivity of the solution was determined. This process was repeated with successive additions of the solute to make the solutions of approximately the required concentration.

The above procedure was followed in all cases except with sulphuric acid monohydrate and the sodium derivative of triethanolamine. In the former case, a stock solution of known strength was made by adding a weighed quantity of freshly prepared $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ to pure triethanolamine and weighing out the required quantities of this stock solution into the cell. In the latter case the stock solution was made by reacting the warm solvent with a freshly cut piece of pure sodium metal, washed several times with anhydrous alcohol and finally twice with triethanolamine, the

concentration being afterwards estimated by titration. The solutions were preserved in a ground-stoppered dropping bottle in a vacuum desiccator.

In all cases the conductivities of the solutions were corrected for the conductivity of the solvent which was measured immediately before adding electrolytes.

The Determination of the Dielectric Constants.—The dielectric constant of triethanolamine was measured in a very simple apparatus used by Nagamani and Jatkar (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1941, 24A, 81). The dielectric constant for triethanolamine was found to be 22.36.

The viscosity of triethanolamine was determined by Noll and Holz (*Papier-Faber Tech. Zeit.*, 1935, 193) who found it to be 8.27 poises at 25°.

Preparation and Purification of the Materials

Triethanolamine.—Reidcl's pure triethanolamine was first distilled under a pressure of 2 mm. The middle portion of the distillate was collected and was subjected to the purification process recommended by Germann and Knight (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 4150). Triethanolamine was carefully neutralised with concentrated hydrochloric acid at 10–15° and a very slight excess of acid, as shown by litmus paper, was used. In an hour the pure crystals of triethanolamine hydrochloride separated and were filtered off under suction, thoroughly washed with 95% alcohol and dried at 110°. The conversion of the hydrochloride into the free base was effected by sodium hydroxide in isopropyl alcohol as almost all the sodium chloride formed could be separated by cooling; triethanolamine hydrochloride (100 g.) was added to 400 c.c. of isopropyl alcohol containing an equivalent quantity of sodium hydroxide. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 4 hours and allowed to stand overnight. It was then cooled in an ice-bath and the separated sodium chloride filtered on a suction filter. The isopropyl alcohol was then distilled off at atmospheric pressure after which the triethanolamine itself distilled over at about 208° at 10 mm. pressure. The yield was more than 90%. Triethanolamine, thus obtained, was further distilled twice under 2mm. at 175°. A very pale straw coloured oily liquid of sp. gr. 1.1239 was obtained.

B. p. (found)
176°
208°

Pressure.
2 mm.
10 mm.

B. p. (from literature)
175°
208°

The freshly distilled triethanolamine had a specific conductivity of 2.23×10^{-7} mhos which on keeping and with occasional short exposures rose to 4.3×10^{-7} mhos in the course of three months.

Tetraethylammonium Chloride.—A pure sample from B.D.H. was recrystallised twice from water and twice from methyl alcohol, as recommended by Hartley *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). It was dried by heating it to 80° and kept in a desiccator under vacuum.

Tetraethylammonium Chlorate.—Pure crystallised barium chlorate was treated with an equivalent amount of pure silver sulphate. The mixture after boiling was filtered. The filtrate, free from sulphate, was then used for carefully neutralising a solution of tetraethylammonium chloride using potassium chromate as an external indicator. The silver chloride was separated by filtration, the tetraethylammonium chlorate was crystallised from the filtrate. It was then recrystallised from water and

dried as above. It was tested for chloride and sulphate and was found to be free from them.

Tetramethylammonium chloride and chlorate were prepared in the same way as the corresponding tetraethyl salts.

Tetramethylammonium Perchlorate.—Pure silver nitrate was treated with pure caustic soda, the precipitated silver oxide was filtered and washed free of alkali. A slight excess of oxide was then heated with 60% perchloric acid, the solution of silver perchlorate was then filtered and evaporated till crystals began to form. The liquor was cooled and crystals separated by filtration. It was recrystallised from benzene and dried at 120° for 12 hours. The salt was then prepared by double decomposition as above.

Ethylamine Hydrochloride.—B.D.H. pure sample was recrystallised from water twice and dried at 80° in vacuum.

Sulphuric acid monohydrate ($H_2SO_4 \cdot H_2O$) was prepared by mixing A.R. fuming acid with A.R. redistilled 95% acid in a specially designed conductivity cell until the proper conductivity corresponding to the monohydrate was observed.

The solution of sodium derivative was prepared as already stated.

Triethanolamine hydrochloride was prepared by neutralising a cooled solution of pure triethanolamine with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The product was recrystallised from water and dried at 120°, m. p. 177°.

The experimental data are recorded in Tables I-X. In the tables the vertical column I gives the concentration of the electrolyte in g. equivalent per litre (c) and column II, equivalent conductivity (λ_r).

Extrapolation for λ_0 .—The Debye-Hückel-Onsager's equation has been applied to get an approximate value of λ_0 in every case. For this, λ_r was plotted as ordinate against $\sqrt{c}$ (Fig. 1). From these curves λ_0 was obtained by extrapolating to zero concentration of the electrolyte. As Onsager's equation gives correct values of λ_0 only for strong electrolytes at large dilution, the values of λ_0 , obtained in the present investigation where only moderate concentrations were used, may not be accurate.

The slope of each curve was calculated and recorded as x_{obs} . The Debye-Hückel-Onsager's equation for uni-univalent electrolytes may be represented by $\lambda_r = \lambda_0 - x\sqrt{c}$ where x is the theoretical slope of the curve and is equal to

$$\left\{ \frac{5.78 \times 10^8}{(DT)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \lambda_0 + \frac{58.0}{\eta_r (DT)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right\} \sqrt{2}$$

For triethanolamine at 25°, where $\eta = 8.27$ poises and $D = 29.36$,

$$x = \lambda_0 + 0.1059.$$

The theoretical slope, x_{obs} , was calculated in every case and the percentage deviation δ , was then calculated as

$$\delta = \frac{x_{obs} - x_{obs}}{x_{obs}} \cdot 100.$$

At the top of each table the values of λ_0 , x and δ are given. Fuoss and Kraus method was also tried to get more accurate values of λ_0 and γ in case where the λ_0 — $\sqrt{c}$ plot

was not a straight line. According to Fuoss and Kraus the conductance of a binary electrolyte as a function of concentration may be represented by

$$\lambda_c = \gamma (\lambda_0 - z \sqrt{c\gamma}) \quad (i)$$

exactly up to the concentration at which specific interactions of higher order than pair-wise become appreciable. (This concentration is of the order of magnitude $3.2 \times 10^{-7} D^3$ at 25° where D =dielectric constant of the solvent). If we know λ_0 and z , and measure λ_c as a function of c , equation (i) permits us to determine γ , the degree of dissociation as a function of c . Instead of solving equation (i) by algebraic method, the method of successive approximation was adopted by Fuoss and Kraus (*loc. cit.*) which may be briefly described thus :

By introducing a new variable z , defined as

$$z = z\lambda_0^{-\frac{3}{2}} \sqrt{c\lambda_c} \quad (ii)$$

where z =Onsagar's slope, λ_0 =limiting conductance, λ_c and c have their usual significance, equation (i) may be rewritten as

$$\gamma = \frac{\lambda_c}{\lambda_0} / F(z) \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

$$\text{where} \quad F(z) = \frac{2}{3} \cos^2 \frac{1}{2} \cos^{-1} \left(-3 \sqrt{3} \frac{z}{2} \right). \quad \dots \quad (iv)$$

In order to obtain λ_0 from conductance data, λ_0^{∞} obtained by the extrapolation of $\lambda_0 - \sqrt{c}$ curve was taken. With this tentative value of λ_0^{∞} , z was calculated using equation (ii), $F(z)$ was found from equation (iv) and used in evaluating γ using equation (iii) and then the activity coefficient was calculated from

$$-\log 10 f_{\pm}^{\pm} = \beta \sqrt{c\gamma} / 1 + \delta \sqrt{c\gamma} \quad \dots \quad (v)$$

$$\text{where} \quad \beta = 0.4343 \cdot \frac{e^2}{2DkT} \left(\frac{8\pi N e^2}{1000DkT} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \text{and} \quad \delta = \left(\frac{8\pi N e^2}{1000DkT} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

[Here $e = 4.770 \times 10^{-10}$ e.s.u. ; $N = 6.06 \times 10^{23}$; k = Boltzmann constant = 1.371×10^{-7} erg/degree ; D = dielectric constant of the solvent ; T = absolute temperature ; a = ionic radius]

Finally $F(z)/\lambda_c$ was plotted against $c \lambda_c f_{\pm}^{\pm} / F(z)$

This method was tried with all the electrolytes not giving a straight line plot of $\lambda_c - \sqrt{c}$.

Usual γ , z and $F(z)$ values could be obtained in the dilute region only, the critical concentration in the case of triethanolamine being 8.0×10^{-3} g. equivalents. Finally $F(z)/\lambda_c$ was plotted against $c \lambda_c f_{\pm}^{\pm} / F(z)$. For only two or three concentrations in the dilute region, a straight line was obtained, with intercept $1/\lambda_0$ from the relation

$$\frac{F(z)}{\lambda_c} = \frac{1}{k\lambda_0^{\frac{3}{2}}} \cdot \frac{c\lambda_c f_{\pm}^{\pm}}{F(z)} + \frac{1}{\lambda_0}$$

FIG. 1

Curves I-IX refer respectively to Et_4NCl , Et_4NClO_4 , $\text{EtNH}_2\cdot\text{HCl}$, HCl , H_2SO_4 , Na , Me_3NCl , Me_3NClO_4 , and Me_3NClO_4 .

λ_c thus found is given at the head of the tables.

TABLE I

Electrolyte: Et_4NCl .
 $\lambda_0 = 0.218$. $T = 25^\circ$. $x_{\text{obs}} = 0.3219$. $x_{\text{obs}} = 0.04$.
 $\delta = -87.6\%$

$c \cdot 10^3$	$\lambda_c \cdot 10^3$
28.5	20.95
76.45	20.5
204.0	20.40
545.0	18.77
809.8	18.5

TABLE II

Electrolyte: Et_4NClO_4 .
 $\lambda_0 = 0.311$. $T = 25^\circ$. $x_{\text{obs}} = 0.4189$. $x_{\text{obs}} = 0.128$.
 $\delta = -69.3\%$

$c \cdot 10^3$	$\lambda_c \cdot 10^3$
8.41	30.61
21.27	29.16
38.50	28.98
57.89	28.08
84.68	27.26
101.70	27.02

TABLE III

Electrolyte: Me_3NCl .
 $\lambda_0 = 0.106$. $T = 25^\circ$. $x_{\text{obs}} = 0.2118$. $x_{\text{obs}} = 0.046$.
 $\delta = -78.3\%$

$c \cdot 10^3$	$\lambda_c \cdot 10^3$
7.805	10.23
37.25	9.594
86.58	8.744
192.7	8.570
360.8	7.684

TABLE IV.

Electrolyte: Me_3NClO_4 .
 $T = 25^\circ$. $x_{\text{obs}} = 0.2879$.
 $x_{\text{obs}} = 0.44$. $\lambda_0 = 0.182$.
 $\delta = +52.8\%$

$c \cdot 10^3$	$\lambda_c \cdot 10^3$
7.06	14.47
11.18	13.31
16.17	13.15
24.27	12.97

TABLE V

Electrolyte : Me_4NClO_4 .
 $\lambda_{\infty} = 0.189$, $x_{\text{obs}} = 0.2955$.
 $x_{\text{obs}} = 0.30$, $T = 25^\circ$.
 $\delta = +1.5\%$

$c.10^3$	$\lambda_{\infty}.10^3$
6.285	16.4
46.33	13.73
72.40	12.99
130.30	12.18

TABLE VI

Electrolyte : HCl. (as triethanolamine hydrochloride). $\lambda_{\infty} = 0.228$.
 $T = 25^\circ$. $x_{\text{obs}} = 0.3339$.
 $x_{\text{obs}} = 0.18$, $\delta = -46.0\%$

$c.10^3$	$\lambda_{\infty}.10^3$
8.561	20.97
12.01	20.96
16.02	20.78
19.74	20.46

TABLE VII

Electrolyte : $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4. \text{H}_2\text{O}$.
 $\lambda_{\infty} = 0.096$, $T = 25^\circ$. $x_{\text{obs}} = 0.2019$. $x_{\text{obs}} = 0.1841$.
 $\delta = -8.8\%$

$c.10^3$	$\lambda_{\infty}.10^3$
10.23	7.513
28.70	6.674
45.83	5.751
64.27	5.024
74.74	5.053

TABLE VIII

Electrolyte : Na as $(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{OH})_3\text{NC}_2\text{H}_5\text{ONa}$
 $T = 25^\circ$. $\lambda_{\infty} = 0.4184$. $x_{\text{obs}} = 0.5243$. $x_{\text{obs}} = 0.08$.
 $\delta = -84.7\%$

$c.10^3$	$\lambda_{\infty}.10^3$
50.36	39.88
110.00	37.52
182.70	30.04
260.5	24.25

λ_{∞} and Viscosity

The approximate constancy $\lambda_{\infty}\eta_{\infty}$, which is known as Walden's rule (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1906, 55, 207; 1912, 78; 257) has been applied to the experimental results in triethanolamine. The products $\lambda_{\infty}\eta_{\infty}$, obtained with different electrolytes in triethanolamine are compared with the products obtained in other solvents of different viscosities at 25° as shown in Table IX.

TABLE IX

Solvent.	$\lambda_{\infty}\eta_{\infty}$.	Electrolyte.	Solvent.	$\lambda_{\infty}\eta_{\infty}$.	Electrolyte.
Triethanolamine	1.786	Et_3NCl	Triethanolamine	0.794	$\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4. \text{H}_2\text{O}$
"	0.984	Me_4NCl	Ethylalcohol	0.549	Me_4NCl
"	2.570	Et_3NClO_4	"	0.559	$(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7)_4\text{N-picrate}$
"	1.505	Me_4NClO_3	Pyridine	0.637 (20°)	NaI
"	1.583	Me_4NClO_4	Nitromethane	0.77	KI
"	2.570	$\text{Et}_3\text{H}_2\text{N.HCl}$	Water	1.00	Et_3NI
"	1.886	$(\text{C}_7\text{H}_7\text{OH})_3\text{N.HCl}$	Glycol	1.32	Et_3NI

Walden's rule, as originally proposed is empirical, but it has been shown subsequently that this rule is a direct consequence of the application of Stoke's law to the motion of ions. Very large spherical ions would be nearly free from solvation because of the low charge density on their surfaces and the magnitude of their radii would be independent of the nature of the solvent. Such ions would most nearly approximate the ideal condition of spheres moving through homogeneous media, as required by Stoke's law. Ions of small size or of unsymmetrical shape or distribution of charge would be expected to exhibit widest departure from Walden's rule. From the above table we find that Walden's rule fails completely in triethanolamine. In general, as Walden himself pointed out, the deviations are greatest in solvents of high viscosity and also in those of high dielectric constant.

Ionic Mobility in Triethanolamine

Walden (*loc. cit.*) has shown that the product of ionic mobility at infinite dilution (λ°) and the viscosity (η_0) of the solvent at the same temperature, is practically independent of temperature and exhibits less than two-fold variation from solvent to solvent, the product being greatest in water. With $(C_2H_5)_4N^+$ and picrate ions, however, the product λ°, η_0 is independent of the nature of solvents.

Taking a mean value of $\lambda^\circ, \eta_0 = 0.294$ at 25° in the case of $(C_2H_5)_4N^+$ ion, we have the mobility of Et_3N^+ ion in triethanolamine = $0.294/8.27$ as 0.0355 .

Conductivity and Temperature

The effect of temperature on conductivity has been studied by measuring the conductivity of tetramethylammonium perchlorate at different temperatures by making the usual solvent correction for every reading and at every temperature studied. The results are summarised in Table X.

TABLE X

Conc. of tetramethylammonium perchlorate = $6.719 \times 10^{-2}N$.

T	10°	15°	20°	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°	50°	55°	60°
$\lambda_c, 10^3$	4.5	7.21	10.29	13.32	20.03	27.76	37.67	51.4	69.1	89.63	91.37.

The results are plotted by taking T as abscissa and λ_c as ordinate (Fig. 2.). The general trend of the above is quite normal and the curve seems to pass through a maximum, as in most non-aqueous solvents.

FIG. 2.

DISCUSSION

From Tables I to VIII and Fig. 1 we find that in the case of tetramethylammonium chlorate, tetramethylammonium perchlorate and sodium, straight lines of $\lambda, -\sqrt{c}$ plots could not be obtained as demanded by Debye-Hückel-Onsagar's equation. With the other electrolytes, however, straight lines could be obtained. As pointed out before, Onsagar's limiting equation should give straight lines only in the dilute regions. At rather high concentrations, as have been used in the present investigation, the limiting equation of Onsagar can no longer be valid, so that even if the mobility change at higher concentrations be still governed by the same laws, it cannot be calculated with the same degree of accuracy. Further, there is the probability that as we pass from dilute to concentrated solutions, additional factors, which could be completely ignored at large dilutions, will eventually become important. One such factor is the viscosity of the solution and the effect of this is difficult to compute; apart from its direct influence on ionic speeds, it will interfere to some extent at high concentrations with the effect of the interionic forces. An additional possibility is the formation of complex ion.

As usual, it has been tried to get values of λ_0 by extrapolation in all cases either from the free-hand curves, or the straight lines as the case may be. However, we do not claim any degree of accuracy in the values of λ_0 thus obtained for reasons cited before. It has been assumed that the electrolytes studied are all uni-univalent. For the ionisation of sodium derivatives, and $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, the following equations have been assumed.

It will be noticed that the deviations from the limiting square-root law are very large with some electrolytes. For tetramethylammonium perchlorate and $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, the deviations are comparatively very small. These deviations point to the incomplete dissociation or ionic complexes in most of the electrolytes studied.

Next the equations deduced by Fuoss and Kraus by making the necessary corrections for both mass action effects as well as ion-atmospheric effects have been tried. These equations, which are based on the binary equilibrium

should fail at concentrations higher than a critical concentration, determined by the dielectric constant and temperature of the solvent. At 25° , $c_0 = 3.2 \times 10^{-7} D^3$, where c = critical concentration. For triethanolamine, this concentration should be

$8.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ at 25° . For tetramethylammonium chlorate and perchlorate and also for sodium, λ_∞ values have been extrapolated from the curves $F(z)/\lambda_\infty - c\lambda_i/F(z)$ which are drawn with only two or three points in the neighbourhood of the critical concentration.

Table IX shows that the values of $\lambda_{0.70}$ are, for all the electrolytes studied, greater than 0.70, a value obtained in most of the non-aqueous solvents of low viscosity.

As a tentative explanation we may suggest like Elliott and Fuoss (*loc. cit.*) that the effective greater mobility in triethanolamine is due to slipping. In solvents of low viscosity, e.g. ethylene chloride, acetone etc, the solute ions are much larger than the solvent molecules and the physical approximation that the solvent is a continuous medium is to some extent, at least, justified. In triethanolamine, on the other hand, the approximation seems no longer permissible, because solvent molecules are now larger than or are of the same order of magnitude as the ions and for that reason a modification of the simpler hydrodynamics becomes necessary. The most obvious correction that is necessary is to make allowance for the greater probability of a small ion passing through large solvent molecules of certain configuration without displacing them and this slipping will naturally lead to an effective greater mobility.

From Table X we find that the equivalent conductivity reaches a maximum value and then it decreases with increasing temperature (Fig.2). In the main these changes are undoubtedly due to changes in the viscosity and dielectric constant of the solvent. The large increase in equivalent conductivity is due to the increased ionic mobility as a result of lowering of viscosity and the simplification of complexes. But with increase in temperature, the dielectric constant, and hence the dissociation power also diminishes and from the maximum point onwards, the latter effect outweighs the former and it is known that as its critical temperature is approached, the solvent becomes almost a perfect insulator.

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